

Europe's first captive breeding of the Black Wood Turtle, *Rhinoclemmys funerea*

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Illustrations by the author

INTRODUCTION

In the year 2000 the black wood turtle, *Rhinoclemmys funerea*, was successfully bred in captivity for the first time in the Netherlands. As far as I can tell this is also the first time this species has been captive bred in Europe (De Bruin, Wicker, pers. comm.). Containing 21 genera, the Old World pond turtles of the family Bataguridae form the largest turtle family in the world. All genera occur in Europe, North Africa, and Asia, with the exception of the genus *Rhinoclemmys*, which is found in Central and South America.

Rhinoclemmys funerea portrait.

Rhinoclemmys funerea has long been known as *Geoemyda funerea*. The genus *Geoemyda* formerly contained numerous species from both the Old and New World. MCDOWELL (1964) showed that the American species differ sufficiently from the Asian species to warrant a new classification. The Old World animals are now placed in the genera *Geoemyda*, *Heosemys*, and *Melanochelys*; the genus *Rhinoclemmys* – with nine species and eight subspecies – is known only from Central and South America. Some species of the latter genus are renowned for producing a single, extremely large, egg per clutch. Even though these

animals can produce an egg measuring up to 8x4 cm, the females rarely reach a size of over twenty centimetres. Publications on *Rhinoclemmys funerea* are very rare and little is known about their ecology and behaviour. SCHAFFER (2000) suspects that – apart from the export ban in some Central and South American countries – this is caused by the fact that few turtle hobbyists are interested in species of *Rhinoclemmys*. In addition, these animals are known to be difficult to maintain in captivity. The aforementioned author is of the opinion that captive *Rhinoclemmys* are often kept at too low a temperature. Another important factor is that these animals often are in very poor health when they finally make it into the pet trade, as is the case with, for instance, *Cuora galbinifrons* (e.g. DE BRUIN, 1994).

DISTRIBUTION

Rhinoclemmys funerea is found in Central America, in the Caribbean lowlands of Costa Rica, and in adjacent Nicaragua and Panama. This species is also known from the Panamanian Bastimentos Island. It inhabits swamps, ponds, streams, and rivers in humid forested areas. MUDDE (1983) encountered this species in the canals of Tortuguero, among

other places. The animals were seen basking on logs in late afternoon, and appeared to be relatively shy. Upon approaching to within twenty meters of these turtles, they rapidly disappeared into the water.

DESCRIPTION

As their common name implies, wood turtles lead a more or less terrestrial life. Some species barely swim and are even less adept at diving. The well-developed skin between the toes of *Rhinoclemmys funerea* indicates that this species inhabits swampy areas. Of all turtles in its genus, *Rhinoclemmys funerea* is the most aquatic species. These turtles may reach a carapace length of over thirty centimetres, making it the largest species in its genus. Their streamlined carapace is domed, but much less so than in most terrestrial species, and is dark brown to black.

This black coloration led to the species name *funerea* (the Latin word 'funeris' means 'burial, shroud'). The plastron is dark as well, with a variable yellow margin around each scute. A light line runs along the centre of the plastron. The bridge has a dark coloration. The lower jaw, throat, legs, and soft parts are yellow with numerous dark lines, spots, and dots. The top of the head is dark brown, as are the eyes. A reddish brown stripe running posteriorly from the eye may or may not be present. In some animals this stripe is broken up into two consecutive longitudinal spots. Contrary to the impression one gets from the genus name *Rhinoclemmys*, the snout barely protrudes. The keratin layer on the upper jaw is serrated.

MY ANIMALS

Roughly thirty years ago I obtained a female *Rhinoclemmys funerea*. I estimated the animal to have a carapace length of twelve to fifteen centimetres. Over the years, the turtle has reached a carapace length of 26 cm, and weighs over three kilograms. This turtle consumes large amounts of both vegetable and animal matter.

Although I have spent many years looking for a male, it was not until April 1998 that I managed to obtain a nice male specimen through Ron de Bruin. This animal had a carapace length of 23 centimetres and weighed two kilograms. Apart from being smaller, the male is also distinguished from the female by its slightly concave plastron and longer, thicker tail. After keeping the male in quarantine for a number of weeks, the two animals were placed together.

MATING AND COURTSHIP

Courtship in *Rhinoclemmys funerea* is not very spectacular and is a relatively quiet event. The male approaches the female from behind and smells her tail base profusely. If she is not immediately willing to mate, he will follow directly behind her throughout the terrarium or the water basin of the outdoor enclosure. Often, after a long chase – especially in the outdoor enclosure – the male will eventually mount the female. While holding on to the female with his claws, the male holds his head low and moves it along the anterior margin of the female's carapace in a vibrating and undulating fashion. Intense jerking head

movements alternate these motions. After a while, the male suddenly slides back with his front limbs roughly halfway down the female's carapace and attempts to mate.

Mating in the water basin.

The neck region of the female is also sniffed intensely. While doing this, the male displays rapid up-and-down movements with his head and sometimes he displays 'threatening' behaviour with his mouth open. The male then places himself diagonally in front of the female, still sniffing her neck and bobbing his head, and mounts her again in an attempt to mate.

The duration of the mating is usually short, no more than a few minutes. In early July the first mating attempts were observed in the outdoor enclosure, and they occurred twice in one hour. Many more matings or attempts to mate were observed in both the indoor terrarium as well as in the outdoor

enclosure. True copulation, during which the reproductive organ of the male entered the female's cloaca, is recognisable when both the male and female withdraw their heads deep inside their carapace.

THE TERRARIA

The terraria in which I maintain my turtles are usually not bigger than 100x40x40 cm. Though this does not allow for much space for each animal, it does not seem to influence the well-being of the turtles since they are mating and laying eggs. Over the last ten years I have successfully bred eight different turtle species under these conditions. The suspended land section takes up about 1/3 of the surface area of each terrarium, and is filled with eight-centimetre deep layer of river sand. Above the land section, I place a regular 60 W light bulb that burns for eight hours per day and insures that the local temperature rises to about 35°C. A fluorescent tube light illuminates the terrarium eight hours per day in the winter months and this photoperiod is gradually increased to 16 hours during the summer months. Even with tropical species, I abstain from heating the water basin. On nice days during the summer, when the temperature exceeds 25°C, the animals are transferred to an outside enclosure. However, one should always be careful with tropical species. After a few cooler days or nights the animals often start to froth at the mouth, and it is imperative that they are moved back inside as soon as possible. Mating and oviposition also take place in the outdoor enclosures.

Basking turtles in the outdoor enclosure.

THE FIRST EGGS

The first clutch of eggs was produced around the middle of October 1998. The eggs were not buried, but rather laid on top of the soil. The hard-shelled eggs measured, on average, 54 mm by 33 mm. Their weight averaged around 36 grams. One egg was already damaged. The remaining good egg was placed in a double-boiler type incubator on a vermiculite substrate. The thermostat was regulated at approximately 30°C. Within a time period of two weeks, five additional clutches of one egg each were deposited. Some were

laid on top of the soil, others in the water. None of the eggs were fertilised. Meanwhile, the frequent mating attempts continued - especially after replacing the water in the basin. A second clutch was deposited during the first week of August 1999. This clutch also turned out to be unfertilised. At the time, the animals were staying in the outdoor enclosure. The first egg was found on top of the soil. The second egg was laid without even attempting to dig a nest cavity. Since I happened to be present at the time, I managed to catch it with my hand. Just to be sure, I transferred the animal inside. Two days later a nest cavity was dug in the indoor terrarium into which four eggs were deposited.

FERTILISED

The eggs are carefully covered.

and laid five eggs. The eggs were placed in an incubator and after a few days a white spot developed on the eggs, which gradually spread onto about half of the shell.

The fairly large eggs of *Rhinoclemmys funerea*.

The first fertilised clutch was produced in the second half of July 2000, after the female had been very restless for a number of days. Every once in a while she would start to excavate a depression with her front limbs and inspect the cavity by pressing her nose deeply into the sand. In addition, she would continually climb onto the land area only to return to the water immediately. By doing this, she turned the relatively dry land area into a big mud puddle. When the groin area of the female was carefully checked, eggs could be clearly felt. After replacing the sand in the land area again and again, the female suddenly started to excavate a nest cavity and laid five eggs. The eggs were placed in an incubator and after a few days a white spot developed on the eggs, which gradually spread onto about half of the shell. In a later stage, this process continued in some of the eggs, turning them completely white. One month later, upon checking the eggs, only one egg displayed developing veins. Another three weeks later this egg clearly contained a live embryo. Even though the other eggs did not display any veins, I still left them in the incubator. As long as they did not develop fungus or start to smell bad there could still be a chance of diapause, or postponed development. However, in spite of the development of a beautiful white band in the shell the remainder of the eggs never developed an embryo. I assume that the developmental process had stopped in an early stage.

THE SECOND CLUTCH

Near the end of August the female started showing her familiar restlessness, and soon she commenced digging a cavity with her front limbs and sniffing the sand. During the first week of September she even produced a second clutch. Approximately seven weeks after depositing her first clutch of the season, the female excavated another nest site and within fifteen minutes she laid six eggs.

It was striking that the date of oviposition moved up each time; each clutch was deposited a few weeks earlier than the previous one. All eggs displayed the familiar white band after a few days, and in five out of six eggs veins were eventually visible.

OFFSPRING

After incubating for approximately eighty days at a temperature of around 30°C, the young hatched. The yolk was almost completely resorbed by each hatchling. The baby turtles measured on average 54 mm in carapace length, with a shell width of 45 mm and a weight of 24 grams. Their dark beige and somewhat marbled carapace displayed a pronounced keel, which is coloured a shade darker than the rest of the shell. The vertebral scutes and costal scutes have a coarser surface structure than the marginal scutes and were traced by a light marginal line. This latter feature makes the hatchlings appear as if they are born with growth rings. The temporal region is adorned with an orangish stripe which, in some cases, is interrupted to form two spots. A thin yellow stripe runs from the corner of the mouth over the eardrum (tympanum). The beautiful yellow coloration of the throat, legs, and soft parts of the adult animals is much less pronounced in juveniles. In comparison with the carapace the tail is relatively short. Something very striking in four of the six juveniles is the inexplicable deep indentation in the abdominals. This indentation extends until the bridge that connects carapace and plastron, and in one individual it reached a depth of no less than 9 mm. The characteristic yellow band that runs along the centre of the plastron in adults is absent from very young individuals.

Hatching after 80 days of incubation.

A well-developed hatchling.

RAPID GROWTH

The little turtles were placed in a plastic terrarium with a layer of water. The water level was maintained at a depth where the juveniles could just raise the tip of their snout above the water when standing on their hind limbs. When the water level is too low this increases the chances of drowning (HOFSTRA, 1996). A 40 W light bulb ensures that the water temperature reaches approximately 28°C. This is a relatively high temperature, but I assume that in nature the hatchlings occupy the warm upper stratum of the water column. At this high water temperature it is necessary to feed the turtles twice a day. At night, the light is turned off and the water temperature drops to 18-19°C. A piece of slate that protrudes somewhat above the water level serves as a land area, and is located directly below the light bulb. However, initially the hatchlings barely used the land area. As the animals grow, their desire to bask seems to increase somewhat. However, no prolonged basking was observed at all. Rearing the young did not pose any problems. Just like their parents, the juveniles turned out to be good eaters. After a week, the first growth rings appear and after a month the birth weight doubled. After approximately two months, the juveniles were larger and heavier than, for example, my six year old, slow-growing offspring of *Chinemys nigricans* (see: HOFSTRA, 1998). In that respect they are much more like juvenile *Cuora amboinensis* (HOFSTRA, 1994). I have found this species to grow explosively by five or six centimetres per year in my care. At an age of barely six months it

became clear that this would be the last time I could measure the juveniles with my regular slide ruler, since the average carapace was already 12 cm long. Their shell width now measured 9.5 cm, and the animals weighed around 250 grams. When the animals reached exactly one year of age, some weighed in at around 400 grams with a length of 14 cm. The food I give to my animals includes earthworms, boiled meat, shrimp, cod filet, chicken breast, baitfish, and pieces of dry cat food – all cut to an appropriate size. The vegetable part of their diet consists of tomatoes, lettuce, apples, kiwi fruit, bananas, dandelion leaves, and even mushrooms – although the latter are not as popular. As a source of extra calcium, ground up eggshells are constantly available in the water. These are eaten in especially large quantities when freshly added to the water. Additionally, I add an AD₃-vitamin solution (brand name Petaid) to the water for my first year offspring. It should be noted that all my juvenile turtles move outside in a wash basin when the weather is sunny and the temperature reaches 25°C so they can enjoy some real sunshine. However, I am always careful to ensure that part of the wash basin is in the shade. In order to prevent escapes and predation, the wash basin is covered with a screen.

Basking *Rhinoclemmys funerea*.

FERTILISED EGGS 2001

Upon carefully probing the groin area of the female in June of 2001, I could feel that she once again contained eggs. During the first week of July, six eggs were deposited in the indoor terrarium. Contrary to the previous clutch, I decided to divide the eggs over two incubators with respective temperatures of 26 and 32°C. The reason for this action was to reduce the risk of all hatchlings being of the same sex. After several days, all eggs displayed the characteristic white band indicating that the eggs were fertilised. Some eggs eventually turned completely white. Both the partially white and the completely white eggs eventually hatched. In retrospect, one egg turned out to be not fertilised, whereas another egg contained a dead embryo. The eggs incubated at approximately 32°C again took about 80 days to hatch; the eggs incubated at 26°C hatched after 127 days. The two juveniles that were incubated at 32°C displayed the same indentations in their plastron, whereas the individuals incubated at 26°C did not. However, at both incubation temperatures one young hatched with an aberrant dorsal pattern.

Juvenile.

Year and month	Number of eggs in clutch	Number of unfertilised eggs	Number of hatchlings	Additional notes
1998, 13 October	7	7	-	Eggs not buried
1999, 1 August	6	6	-	Four eggs buried
2000, 22 July	5	4	1	All eggs buried
2000, 7 September	6	1	5	All eggs buried
2001, 5 July	6	1	4	1 embryo died
total	30	19	10	

Table: Egg clutches produced by the black wood turtle, *Rhinoclemmys funerea*.

Three five months-old hatchlings.

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